

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MOST IMPORTANT TPPs FOR PERFORMING GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE AND SCIENTIFIC CALCULATIONS IN PYTHON PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Python (mainly Payton "and sometimes pronounced such as" python ") is developed by Guido Van Rossum in 1991. There are so many positive aspects of this language that the number does not end. First of all, Python is universal, this language can be written in various programs in this language. And the programs written in this language can work very easily in any operating system. In addition, Python fully meets the modern requirements of programming, its structural, object-oriented, functional and imperative are from OSAs advantages. One of the most advantages of Python language is that it is very easy to learn this language

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1.1 Graphical user interface (GUI) in the Python programming environment

First of all, for the convenience of the user (programming, testing, etc.), Python has a very popular basic programming environment (Python shell) at the level of interactive shell IDLE (Integrated Development Environment) Here, similar to Matlab, as a "calculator" from the command line can also be used. To write any calculation expressions and get the result, it is enough to press the "Enter" key of my keyboard, fig. 1.1.


```
Python 3.7.6 Shell
File Edit Shell Debug Options Window Help
Python 3.7.6 (tags/v3.7.6:43364a7ae0, Dec 19 2019, 00:42:30) [MSC v.1916 64 bit
(AMD64)] on win32
Type "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> 34+2*(14-125)
-188
>>> |
```

Figure 1.1. Python's traditional programming environment IQI: IDLE (Integrated Development Environment)

The Python programming environment has its own (that is, in the same IDLE IQI) special Python editor. If you need to call that editor to compile the program, you need to use IDLE's File menu. The New File command is selected from the menu (or by pressing the Ctrl+N keys from the keyboard). In the window that opens, it is possible to compile the program code, test it, and use ready-made programs, fig. 1.1.2.


```
ODE_NonlinearPendulum.py
File Edit Format Run SubCode Options Window Help
1 # Created on Sun Jul 5 19:30:37 2020
2 from scipy.integrate import odeint
3 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4 import numpy as np
5 # ADTS-i ifadə edən Python funksiyasını yaradırıq:
6 reqqas = lambda y,t: [y[1], -0.5*y[1]-10*np.sin(y[0])]
7 v0=5 # başlanğıc sürət
8 t = np.linspace(0,20,401)
9 [y1,y2]=odeint(reqqas, [0, v0], t, full_output=False).T
10 # Zamanın asılı həllin birgə qrafiki: fi = fi(t) və dfi(t)/dt.
11 plt.figure()
12 plt.close('all')
13 plt.plot(t, y1, 'r', label='fi(t)')
14 plt.plot(t, y2, 'b', label='dfi(t)/dt')
15 plt.legend(loc='best')
16 plt.xlabel('t')
17 plt.grid()
18 # Dinamik sistem hərəkatının faza portreti: fi = fi(dfi/dt)
19 plt.figure()
```

Figure 1.2. Programming editor of Python IDLE IQI (in this environment it is also possible to get graphs of obtained numerical results)

However, the reader should be aware that the same WinPython complex package also has other IQI-type wrappers for working comfortably in the Python language. For example, IQIs such as the more popular Pyzo and Spyder make it very convenient and convenient to write, test, and operate Python programs. fig. 1.1.2. shown in a and b.

a)

b)

Figure 1.1.2. Additional IQIs of the Python programming language:

a) Spyder programming environment;

b) Piezo programming environment.

So, where is the best place for the user (that is, the reader of the book) to download the Python programming language itself and the scientific application programs (TPPs) written in Python used in this book? First of all, of course, you can visit the website of the Python language developers <https://www.python.org/downloads/>. In the new Python versions, there is a special small program utility for downloading the desired TPP from the Internet, and its name is PIP. So, it is important to have that PIP utility in the first place. In the second step, this method mainly applies to readers working with Windows OS, in the command line of the Windows CMD or Windows Power Shell command line window available in Windows 10 OS, it is enough to type such a command (for example, the name TPP in the example is written), the user should write here the

name of the TPP he is interested in, for example matplotlib, mayavi kuni, etc.)» `pip install TPP_name`

So, in automatic mode, you can download the necessary TPP from the Internet. But a more convenient way is to use the Python 3 version of the programming environment, especially considering that most readers' PCs are running Microsoft Windows. On the other hand, if you are interested in the application of Python in scientific computing, then this is the better way. To download Python itself, its TPPs more commonly used in scientific computing, plus 101s like Pyzo, Spyder, on computers running Windows OS, visit this site: <http://winpython.sourceforge.net/>. The name of that application package is WinPython. If the user needs additional TPP for some reason (for example, you need to use astropy TPP to perform astronomical calculations), then you can easily use the method I showed above. The

user (ie, specifically, the reader of this book) should take into account that the version of Python 3 that he downloads will be one of the last stable versions. The downloaded program and TPPs will be in portable form (that is, the user can place the program anywhere on his computer, even transfer it to his personal flash card if he wants). It is better to download Python version 3.7.6 and higher TPPs from that site on Windows 10 OS computer.

SciPy is the most important TPP library for performing scientific calculations in the Python programming environment

Currently, the Python programming language is used as the core language in the SciPy application program package (TPP), which is known as the most fundamental tool in scientific computing.

SciPy is a library of open-source application packages that includes high-quality scientific tools based on the Python programming language. SciPy actually stores the optimization, integration, special functions, flexible Fourier transforms, signal processing, image processing, ordinary differential equation solving, genetic algorithms used in science and engineering computing in the form of modules, like MATLAB and Scilab.

The main modules (or TPPs) of the SciPy library are:

- constants - stores physical and fundamental mathematical constants;
- is a set of procedures that perform cluster-vector quantization;
- fftpack is a collection of routines that perform discrete Fourier transform;
- integrate-tools for integration;
- interpolate are tools for interpolation;
- io - data input-output;
- lib - Python wrappers for external libraries,
- linalg - consists of procedures that perform the numerical solution of linear algebra problems;
- misc - includes various utilities;
- optimize - is a set of procedures that execute optimization procedures;
- sandbox - is a collection of experimental codes;
- signal - contains procedures intended for signal processing;
- sparse is a set of procedures for performing numerical operations on sparse matrices;
- special - is a set of special functions;
- stats - is a set of procedures that perform statistical calculations;
- weave- consists of procedures that perform the numerical solution of wave propagation problems;

Additional functionality of the SciPy library includes the following capabilities:

Scientific graphics. 2D scientific graphics from the Matplotlib package is currently the most recommended method. But HippoDraw, Chaco, and Biggles do can be used to create 2D graphics. For 3D scientific visualization iso Python Imaging Library vo MayaVi is very popular.

Optimization. SciPy has its own elements for optimization, but OpenOpt provides a large number of optimization packages.

With the help of state-of-the-art data analysis RPy, SciPy R's statistical package interface was designed for complex data analysis.

Database. SciPy can interact with PyTables, designed to efficiently manage large volumes of hierarchical data stored in HDFS files.

It should be noted that there is still a large number of standard libraries (TPP) based on the Python language. They are used all over the world, to one degree or another, as the most important tools for conducting computer modeling. Many of them may not be included in TPP SciPy. In this case, the user should download the scientific TPPs that interest him by the rules recommended above. Below is a list of all TPPs that work with the Python core, with explanations:

Interactive shell. IPython provides a MATLAB-like style of code generation and processing in an interactive environment.

Symbolic mathematics (performing analytical calculations). There are several libraries available for Python. Like PyDSTool, Symbolic, and SymPy

SciPy is a freely licensed library of open source TPPs for mathematics, natural sciences, and engineering (scientific TPPs are a repository).

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CherryPy ("Cerripayin" [teri pai], pun: ing cherry pie is "cherry pie"), is an object-oriented Web-framework written in the Python programming language. It is designed for rapid development of Web-applications (programs) for the Internet network. HTTP is a superstructure on top of the protocol, but remains low-level and does not go beyond the scope of RFC 2616 requirements. Cherrypy acts as a standalone Web server or can run under the control of another server plugin that supports the WSGI protocol.

Django - (Django, ['dzæŋɡoo]) - is a loose framework for Web applications in Python that uses the MVC scheduling pattern. The project is supported by the Django Software Foundation. In Django, a site is created from one or more plugins (or programs), which are recommended to be removed and connected. One of the main principles of the framework - DRY (ing Don't repeat yourself). Also, unlike other frameworks, URL handlers in Django are explicitly configured using regular expressions, not automatically inferred from the controller's model structure.

GAE framework is a free framework for web-applications. Initially, the project was created as a Django analogue, fully integrated with Google App Engine and written in Python. In the GAE framework, a site is built from several plugins (or programs). It is recommended to do independent and connected. The GAE framework

uses an ORM from Google App Engine to work with the data store.

Genshi is a Python library that provides a unified set of components for parsing, preparing, and processing HTML, XML, or other textual content on the WEB. Genshi uses some web frameworks, such as CherryPy, TurboGears, Pylons and web2py. Genshi TPP replaces Kid in TurboGears 2.x.

Jinja (pronounced dzindzya) is a templater for the Python programming language. The textual language of these templates, and thus may have been used to create any icon, as well as the source code, is licensed under the BSD. The Jinja templater allows you to set up tags, filters, tests and global variables. Filters are very simple to use by the system (brought to the Unix pipeline).

JPyype is an extension to the Python programming language that gives programs full access to Java class libraries. Unlike Jython, it allows Python extensions to work at the greatest speed.

Matplotlib is a TPP in the Python programming environment for two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) data visualization with clmi graphics. Received images may be used as illustrations in publications.

The Natural Language Toolkit is the NLTK Library, or NTLK, a package of libraries and programs for symbolic and statistical natural language processing written in the Python programming language. Contains graphical representations (visualizations) and samples of data. It is accompanied by extensive documentation, including a book explaining key concepts for those natural language processing tasks that can be accomplished with this package. NTLK is free software.

NumPy is a TPP that adds support for large multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, a collection of high-level mathematical functions and numerical routines for array operations in Python (as in Matlab).

Pygame is a set (assembly) of Python programming language modules designed for writing computer games and multimedia applications (programs). My Pygame multimedia library is SDL-based.

PyGTK is a set of Python bindings for the GTK+ graphical interface library. PyGTK is a self-contained PT.

The main purpose of PyMidas is the TPP designed for the application of the MIDAS package in astronomical calculations. PyNGL is TPP (The University of Illinois/NCSA Open Source license). A module for the Python programming language used for visualization in the geological sciences for high-quality 2D special note scientific data visualization. It is used by the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), a US scientific organization.

PyObjC is a project that allows sharing libraries and classes of such programming languages. Similar to the structure of the Objective-C language.

PyQi-Python is a set of "bindings" of Qt, a graphical framework for the Python programming language, implemented as an extension. PyQt runs on all Q-t supported platforms: Linux and other UNIX-like S, Mac

OS X and Windows: PyQt realizes Qt capabilities practically completely. Over 600 classes, over 6000 functions and methods, including:

- 1) It is an available set of videos of the graphic interface;
- 2) consolidated widget styles.
- 3) Creates access to databases with the help of SQL-m (ODBC, MySQL, PostgreSQL, Oracle);
- 4) QScintilla, a text editor based on Scintilla: support for internationalization (i18n),
- 5) Maintains SVG support,
- 6) Supports Webkit-lo integration, HTML engine,
- 7) supports video and audio files. It also includes PyQt and Or Designer (Qt Creator) and uses it as a designer of the graphical user interface.

It is for developing web applications with open source code written in Python within the Pylons project.

PySide is an API-level Python wrapper around the Qt toolkit in PyQt.

Python Imaging Library (abbreviated as PIL) is a Python language library designed for working with raster graphics. Features of the library: support of binaries, indexed halftone and CMYK-4 of images; Support for BMP formats, EPS, GIF, JPEG, PDF, PNG, PNM, TIFF, ICO, MPEG, PCX, PSD, WMF and others.

SQLAlchemy is a Python programming library for working with application-relative VBIS of this ORM technology. Serves for synchronization of Python objects and relative database writes.

Tkinter is a cross-platform graphics library based on these Tk tools. The standard library includes Python. Tornado is an extensible, non-blocking Web server (written in Python and used as a server and framework).

Twisted supports events-oriented framework written in Python and distributed under the MIT license.

ZODB is a Python-object database (OOBD) object. It is used to organize more symposia, various types of online conferences and lectures (SERN-db is developed and used there).

The list of TPPs related to the scientific field in the Python programming environment given above could be expanded more, but here the most important points should be touched and the reader should be introduced to the most necessary mathematical or scientific TPPs first. From a practical point of view, as we have already talked about at the beginning of Chapter 1, Windows OS computer users, if they download the WinPython package, will be provided with all the basic packages used in scientific work. However, I would like to note that the most basic scientific package is, of course, the SciPy library itself, which contains the main scientific TPPs. The most important Python-based TPP in the scientific field is Numpy. In this TPP, it can be said that, the most important numerical methods are available, from linear algebra to the numerical solution of differential equations, and the programming environment in Numpy is the same as in Matlab. The second important TPP with the application of mathematical methods is SymPy. This TPP is related to the application of analytical mathematical methods in scientific research and the main analytical methods are represented here. Therefore, when researchers need to perform analytical

calculations, they do not need to resort to popular computer software with a proprietary license (i.e. paid for), SymPy can cope with its problem if it knows the TPP at an adequate level.

Finally, as the reader knows, scientific graphics are widely used in the conduct of every scientific work and in the analysis of results: that is, mainly the construction of various types of 2D and 3D graphics is envisaged. In this field, the most used TPP in the Python programming environment is Matplotlib.

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